

THE FRIENDLY GUIDE TO RELEASE 5 FOR PROVIDERS

REVISED EDITION

This guide is a non-intimidating manual for publishers and vendors implementing COUNTER-compliant usage statistics for the first time, or for more experienced hands, implementing new reports or preparing for COUNTER audit.

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The logo for COUNTER, featuring the word "COUNTER" in a blue, sans-serif font. The letter "N" is stylized with a checkmark shape integrated into its top right corner.

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INTRODUCTION

THIS GUIDE IS A friendly introduction to the COUNTER Code of Practice, Release 5, for publishers and other providers. It accompanies The Friendly Guide to Release 5: Technical Notes, which provides an overview of Release 5 implementation and auditing.

Release 5 of the COUNTER Code of Practice is designed to balance changing reporting needs with the need to make things simpler, so that all content providers can achieve compliance and librarians can have usage statistics that are credible, consistent and comparable. For more information, please refer to the full [Code of Practice](#).

WHAT IS COUNTER?

COUNTER stands for

**Counting Online Usage of
NeTworked Electronic Resources.**

Our website is at <http://www.projectcounter.org/>

COUNTER was one of the first, if not the first, standards organisation established for the modern information environment. It has succeeded in bringing together a collaboration of publishers and librarians to develop and maintain the standard for counting the use of electronic resources. It has also ensured that most major publishers and vendors are compliant by providing their library customers around the world with COUNTER usage statistics.

COUNTER publishes the Code of Practice, which is the standard for counting the use of electronic resources, and a register of COUNTER-compliant vendors and publishers. Release 5 of the Code of Practice, which is the subject of this Friendly Guide, is subject to continuous maintenance. As the Release changes, this Guide will be updated.

WHO USES COUNTER REPORTS?

The COUNTER standard was originally developed to provide a service to librarians and other people who purchase subscriptions to publishers' content. The intention was to allow librarians to easily compare their usage across different publishers' content, and let them use that information to calculate a cost-per-download for their subscrip-

tions. COUNTER reports were not originally intended to be used by publishers as a way of measuring usage across their client base, but are increasingly being used for that purpose.

SCENARIO

Camford purchase two journal subscriptions for 2015: Journal X for £25,000 and Journal Y for £10,000. At the end of the year Camford's librarian, Barbara, runs a Release 5 TR_J1 report to check the fulltext usage of each journal, excluding Open Access articles. Journal X is showing 60,000 Unique_Item_Requests, compared with just 200 for Journal Y. Barbara therefore tells her Head Librarian that while Journal X is more expensive, it has a better cost-per-download.

The calculation looks like this:

Journal X £25,000 / 60,000

Journal Y £10,000 / 200

If Camford must choose a journal to cancel, it's likely to be Journal Y.

Academic libraries across the world use COUNTER reports to:

- Inform renewal decisions or new purchasing decisions based on data about usage and access denials
- Inform faculty about the value of the library and its resources
- Understand user behavior and improve user experiences

Most major vendors and publishers also use COUNTER reports to:

- Provide reliable and consistent usage data to their customers
- Upsell using COUNTER data about access denials
- Inform editors and authors about the usage of their publications

HOW IS COUNTER FUNDED AND ORGANIZED?

COUNTER is a not-for-profit membership organization, funded by membership fees and sponsorship.

The membership – publishers, vendors and librarians – lead COUNTER. A Board of Directors has oversight of the financial matters and appoints the Executive Committee to oversee the operation. A Project Director, reporting to the Executive Committee, is responsible for the day-to-day management of COUNTER. The publisher, intermediary and librarian communities are all represented on the Board and on the Executive Committee, as well as on the Technical Advisory Board.

HOW DO I BECOME COUNTER COMPLIANT?

■ Select the relevant reports

There are four ‘Master Reports’ in Release 5 of the COUNTER Code of Practice, each of which has a set of ‘Standard Views’. This Guide will help you select which of the Master Reports and Standard Views are relevant to your platform.

■ Prepare your COUNTER reports

All Master Reports and Standard Views must be available in two formats:

- In tabular form (e.g. as an Excel spreadsheet)
- As machine-readable JSON data via SUSHI

More detail about report formats can be found in The Friendly (Technical) Guide to Release 5.

■ Complete the paperwork

Once you are ready, use the COUNTER Report Validation Tool (available on our website at projectcounter.org/) to check whether your reports are valid. The results of your test and the Declaration of COUNTER Compliance will be needed for your audit.

We also encourage everyone to become a COUNTER member to support our work. You will find both the Membership Application and the Declaration on the website at project-counter.org/.

■ Undergo an independent audit

There are two approved COUNTER auditors—ABC (abc.org.uk) and BPA Worldwide (bpaww.com). COUNTER will also accept an audit by any Chartered Accountant (UK), Certified Public Accountant (USA), or their equivalent elsewhere. Once you have selected your auditor, provide them with access to your prepared reports.

■ Tell your customers you are COUNTER-compliant

Once you have passed your audit, COUNTER will list you on its website and issue you a dated logo stating that you are COUNTER-compliant.

You will need to be audited within six months of signing the Declaration of COUNTER Compliance, and annually thereafter. If you are a very small publisher and will find an annual audit particularly difficult, please get in touch with COUNTER’s Project Director to discuss permission to be audited every other year.

COUNTER METRICS

This section of the guide identifies and explains the complete list of metric types included in Release 5. There is also a brief summary of the new attributes associated with Release 5, which are designed to provide flexibility and eliminate the need for special reports.

USAGE

There are several different types of usage metric in Release 5, which break down into investigations and requests.

An investigation is tracked when a user performs any action in relation to a content item or title, while a request is specifically related to viewing or downloading the full content item (see Figure 1).

Investigations

- 'Total_Item_Investigations': the total number of times a content item or information related to a content item was accessed.
- 'Unique_Item_Investigations': the number of unique content items (e.g. chapters) investigated by a user.
- 'Unique_Title_Investigations': the number of unique book titles investigated by a user.

Requests

- 'Total_Item_Requests': the total number of times the full text of a content item was downloaded or viewed.
- 'Unique_Item_Requests': the number of unique content items (e.g. chapters) requested by a user.
- 'Unique_Title_Requests': the number of unique book titles requested by a user.

SCENARIO

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on Publisher Platform Alpha. From a list of search results she opens three article abstracts and a video record. All four records are different, but two of the articles are from the same journal. The counts are:

- Total_Investigations: 4
- Unique_Item_Investigations: 4
- Unique_Title_Investigations: 0
- Total_Requests: 0
- Unique_Item_Requests: 0
- Unique_Title_Requests: 0

After reading the abstracts, Susan downloads the PDFs for two of the articles, both from the same journal. The counts change to:

- Total_Investigations: 6
- Unique_Item_Investigations: 4
- Unique_Title_Investigations: 0
- Total_Requests: 2
- Unique_Item_Requests: 2
- Unique_Title_Requests: 0

From a cost-per download perspective, Barbara should count the two Unique_Item_Requests.

ACCESS DENIALS

Access denials are sometimes known as turnaways. Two varieties of access denial metric are tracked in Release 5:

- **'No_License':**
counted where a user is unable to access a unique content item because their institution does not have a license to the content.
- **'Limit_Exceeded':**
counted where a user is unable to access a unique content item because their institution's cap on the number of simultaneous users has been exceeded.

Both No_License and Limit_Exceeded apply when a user has successfully investigated an item, but has not been able to complete a request.

SCENARIO

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on Publisher Platform Alpha. From a list of search results, she opens three article abstracts and two video records. Her institution has not subscribed to the video database and she is therefore denied access. The counts are:

- Total_Item_Investigations: 5
- Unique_Item_Investigations: 5
- No_License: 2
- Limit_Exceeded: 0

Susan repeats her attempt to access one of the video records five minutes later. The counts are:

- Total_Item_Investigations: 6
- Unique_Item_Investigations: 5
- No_License: 3
- Limit_Exceeded: 0

High No_License counts may suggest to Barbara that she should investigate the costs of subscribing to the video database.

SCENARIO

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on Publisher Platform Alpha. From a list of search results, she opens three article abstracts and two video records. Her institution has a concurrency-limited subscription to the video database, and Susan's usage exceeds that cap. The counts are:

- Total_Item_Investigations: 5
- Unique_Item_Investigations: 5
- No_License: 0
- Limit_Exceeded: 2

High Limit_Exceeded counts may suggest to Barbara that she should investigate the costs of increasing the concurrency cap for the video database.

SEARCHES

There are four different types of search metric in Release 5:

- **‘Searches_Regular’:**
the number of times a user searches a database, where they have actively chosen that database from a list of options OR there is only one database available to search.
- **‘Searches_Automated’:**
the number of times a user searches a database, where they have not actively chosen that database from a list of options. That is, Searches_Automated is recorded when the platform offers a search across multiple databases by default, and the user has not elected to limit their search to a subset of those databases.
- **‘Searches_Platform’:**
the number of times a user searches a database, regardless of the number of databases involved in the search.
- **‘Searches_Federated’:**
the number of times a search is run remotely through an API.

SCENARIO

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on Publisher Platform Alpha. She runs a search for “history AND antibiotics”. The counts are:

- Searches_Regular: 1
- Searches_Automated: 0
- Searches_Platform: 1
- Searches_Federated: 0

For a database like this, the cost per use calculation may be more dependent on searches than on fulltext downloads – this is dependent on library practice.

SCENARIO

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on Publisher Platform Alpha, which includes multiple databases. She runs a search for “history AND antibiotics”. The counts are:

- Searches_Regular: 0
- Searches_Automated: 1
- Searches_Platform: 1
- Searches_Federated: 0

Susan then selects the ‘History of Medicine’ database and reruns her search. The counts are:

- Searches_Regular: 1
- Searches_Automated: 1
- Searches_Platform: 2
- Searches_Federated: 0

In a separate session, Susan uses an API to search Publisher Platform Alpha. The count for that activity is:

- Searches_Regular: 0
- Searches_Automated: 0
- Searches_Platform: 0
- Searches_Federated: 1

COUNTER MASTER REPORTS AND STANDARD VIEWS

Release 5 of the COUNTER Code of Practice includes four Master Reports covering a very wide spectrum of activities:

1. Platform Master Report
2. Database Master Report
3. Title Master Report
4. Item Master Report

Which of the Master Reports you need to provide will depend on your Host Type. Master Reports cover a wide spectrum of activities, so for ease of use each of the Master Reports has one or more pre-set Standard Views. These are summaries of particular types of activity, such as usage or access denials. While you can filter a Master Report to show a Standard View (or a custom view to suit your needs), Standard Views only hold a subset of the information from a Master Report; it is therefore not possible to ‘unfilter’ a Standard View to obtain its parent Master Report.

Each Master Report includes a complete set of COUNTER metrics, which are discussed in the next section, supplemented with a variety of attributes. There are details of the Master Reports and their Standard Views later in this guide.

REPORT HEADERS

The tabular versions of Release 5 reports have a common format, which looks like this:

Label	Value
Report_Name	Name of the report
Report_ID	Identifier of the report

COUNTER MASTER REPORTS AND STANDARD VIEWS

Release	5
Institution_Name	Name of the institution usage is attributed to
Institution_ID	Identifier(s) for the institution usage is attributed to
Metric_Types	Semicolon-space delimited list of metric types included in the report
Report_Filters	Semicolon-space delimited list of filters applied to the data to generate the report
Report_Attributes	Semicolon-space delimited list of attributes applied to the data to generate the report
Exceptions	Any exceptions that occurred in generating the report
Reporting_Period	Date range covered by the report
Created	Date the report was run
Created_By	Name of organization or system that generated the report
<row left blank>	

It is important to stick to this common report header format, as anything else will not be COUNTER-compliant. For the purposes of this guide we are showing the header and body information separately but in the actual report these would be in the same sheet, with the header in cells A1 to B13 and the body of the report below.

PLATFORM REPORTS

All publishers and vendors must provide a Platform Master Report (PR) showing activity across all metrics for entire platforms. There is one Standard View for the PR.

Identifier	Name	Description
PR_P1	Platform Usage	A pre-set Standard View of PR showing total and unique item requests, as well as platform searches

For the purposes of PR_P1, the PR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: Regular
- Metric_Type: Searches_Platform; Total_Item_Requests; Unique_Item_Requests

PR FILTERS

PR can be filtered on five metrics, as described in the table below. It is also possible to exclude the month-by-month breakdown of activity and show only the total activity for the whole reporting period.

Filter / attribute	Description
Data_Type	All, or one or more of the Data_Types applicable to the platform
Access_Method	All, or one or more of the Access_Methods applicable to the platform
Metric_Type	All, or one or more of the Metric_Types applicable to the platform
exclude_monthly_details	True or False. Show the Reporting_Period_Total column without month-by-month breakdowns

WHAT DOES A PR LOOK LIKE?

PR is a relatively compact report, only five columns across (Platform, Data_Type, Access_Method, Metric_Type, and Reporting_Period_Total) plus monthly breakdowns. Every metric type should be included, but for the purposes of this guide only a subset is shown in the example below.

Example: a PR has been generated for Publisher Platform Alpha (PP α) covering the period from 01 January to 30 June 2017, for Sample University. In this case, users from Sample University have investigated a series of journal and book items but have not attempted to access any fulltext: this means that while there are 15 investigations in total, of 11 unique items, there are no requests in the report. Users have also been denied access to a database on three occasions during the report period.

PLATFORM REPORTS

<http://bit.ly/2EYza4n>

Report_Name	Platform Master Report
Report_ID	PR
Release	5
Institution_Name	Sample University
Institution_ID	isni=1234567890
Metric_Types	<i>as selected</i>
Report_Filters	<i>as selected</i>
Report_Attributes	as selected
Exceptions	
Reporting_Period	2017-01-01 to 2017-06-30
Created	2017-05-25
Created_By	Publisher Platform Alpha

Platform	Data_Type	Access_Type	Access_Method	Metric_Type	Reporting_Period_Total
PPα	Journal	Controlled	Regular	Total_Item_Investigations	10
PPα	Journal	Controlled	Regular	Unique_Item_Investigations	6
PPα	Journal	Controlled	Regular	Unique_Title_Investigations	5
PPα	Book	Controlled	Regular	Total_Item_Investigations	5
PPα	Book	Controlled	Regular	Unique_Item_Investigations	5
PPα	Book	Controlled	Regular	Unique_Title_Investigations	3
PPα	Database	Controlled	Regular	No_License	3

DATABASE REPORTS

Three Host Types need to provide a **Database Master Report** (DR):

1. A&I Database
2. Aggregated Full Content
3. Multimedia Collection

Database Master Reports (DR) show activity across all metrics for entire databases or fixed collections of content which behave like a database. The DR can be filtered according to user needs, and has two Standard Views.

Identifier	Name	Description
DR_D1	Database Search and Item Usage	A pre-set Standard View of DR showing total item investigations and requests, as well as searches
DR_D2	Database Access Denied	A pre-set Standard View of DR showing where users were denied access because simultaneous use (concurrency) licenses were exceeded, or their institution did not have a license for the database

For the purposes of DR_D1, the DR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Metric_Type: searches_automated; searches_federated; searches_regular; total_item_investigations; total_item_requests

For the purposes of DR_D2, the DR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Metric_Type: limit_exceeded; no_license

DR FILTERS

DR can be filtered on five metrics, as described in the table below. It is also possible to exclude the month-by-month breakdown of activity and show only the total activity for the whole reporting period.

Filter / attribute	Description
Data_Type	All, or one or more of the Data_Types applicable to the database
Access_Method	All, or one or more of the Access_Methods applicable to the database
Metric_Type	All, or one or more of the Metric_Types applicable to the database
exclude_monthly_details	True or False. Show the Reporting_Period_Total column without month-by-month breakdowns

WHAT DOES A DR LOOK LIKE?

DRs are less compact than PRs, with nine columns across plus monthly breakdowns. In addition to the columns in PR (Platform, Data_Type, Access_Method, Metric_Type, and Reporting_Period_Total), DR shows the database name within the platform and the publisher details.

Again, every metric type should be included, but for the purposes of this Guide only a subset is shown in the example below.

Example: a DR has been generated for the Multimedia database on Publisher Platform Alpha (PPα) covering the period from 01 January to 30 June 2017, for Sample University. In this case, users from Sample University have investigated eight items in the database, and requested the full record for three of those items. There is also a record of one search of the database during the report period.

<http://bit.ly/2mTfUO5>

Report_Name	Database Master Report
Report_ID	DR
Release	5
Institution_Name	Sample University
Institution_ID	isni=1234567890
Metric_Types	<i>as selected</i>
Report_Filters	<i>as selected</i>

DATABASE REPORTS

Report_Attributes	as selected
Exceptions	
Reporting_Period	2017-01-01 to 2017-06-30
Created	2017-05-25
Created_By	Publisher Platform Alpha

Database	Publisher	Publisher_ID	Platform	Proprietary_ID	Data_Type	YOP	Access_Type	Access_Method	Metric_Type	Reporting_Period_Total
Multimedia	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	ahgoiuaryg	Database	2016	Controlled	Regular	Total_Item_Investigations	8
Multimedia	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	ahgoiuaryg	Database	2016	Controlled	Regular	Unique_Item_Investigations	8
Multimedia	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	ahgoiuaryg	Database	2016	Controlled	Regular	Unique_Title_Investigations	1
Multimedia	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	ahgoiuaryg	Database	2016	Controlled	Regular	Total_Item_Requests	3
Multimedia	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	ahgoiuaryg	Database	2016	Controlled	Regular	Unique_Item_Requests	3
Multimedia	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	ahgoiuaryg	Database	2016	Controlled	Regular	Unique_Title_Requests	1
Multimedia	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	ahgoiuaryg	Database	2016	Controlled	Regular	Searches_Regular	1

TITLE MASTER REPORT

Three Host Types need to provide a Title Master Report (TR):

1. Aggregated Full Content
2. eBook
3. eJournal

A TRA Title Master Report (TR) shows activity across all metrics for entire titles, which may be books or journals. The TR can be filtered according to user needs and has seven Standard Views. In the case of TR, the Standard Views apply to different Host Types – for example, an eJournal host does not need to provide TR_B1. TR has an additional filter, Section_Type, in addition to the five which apply to all of the Master Reports.

Identifier	Name	Description	Host Types
TR_B1	Book Requests (Excluding OA_Gold)	A pre-set book Standard View of TR showing fulltext activity for all content which is not Gold Open Access. Numbers between sites will vary based on whether the content is delivered as a complete book or by chapter.	Aggregated Full Content eBook
TR_B2	Book Access Denied	A pre-set book Standard View of TR showing where users were denied access because simultaneous use (concurrency) licenses were exceeded, or their institution did not have a license for the database	Aggregated Full Content eBook
TR_B3	Book Usage by Access Type	A pre-set book Standard View of TR showing showing all applicable metric types broken down by Access_Type	Aggregated Full Content eBook
TR_J1	Journal Requests (Excluding OA_Gold)	A pre-set journal Standard View of TR showing fulltext activity for all content which is not Gold Open Access.	Aggregated Full Content eJournal

TITLE MASTER REPORT

TR_J2	Journal Accessed Denied	A pre-set journal Standard View of TR showing where users were denied access to journals because simultaneous use (concurrency) licenses were exceeded, or their institution did not have a license for the database	Aggregated Full Content eJournal
TR_J3	Journal Usage by Access Type	A pre-set journal Standard View of TR showing all applicable metric types broken down by Access_Type	Aggregated Full Content eJournal
TR_J4	Journal Requests by YOP (Excluding OA_Gold)	A pre-set journal Standard View of TR breaking down the fulltext usage of non-Gold Open Access content by year of publication (YOP).	Aggregated Full Content eJournal

TITLE REPORT STANDARD VIEWS FOR BOOKS

For the purposes of TR_B1, the TR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Access_Type: controlled
- Data_Type: book
- Metric_Type: total_item_requests; unique_item_requests

For the purposes of TR_B2, the TR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Data_Type: book
- Metric_Type: limit_exceeded; no_license

For the purposes of TR_B3, the TR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Data_Type: book
- Metric_Type: total_item_investigations; total_item_requests, unique_item_investigations; unique_item_requests; unique_title_investigations; unique_title_requests

TITLE REPORT STANDARD VIEWS FOR JOURNALS

For the purposes of TR_J1, the TR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Access_Type: controlled
- Data_Type: journal
- Metric_Type: total_item_requests; unique_item_requests

For the purposes of TR_J2, the TR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Data_Type: journal
- Metric_Type: limit_exceeded; no_license

For the purposes of TR_J3, the TR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Data_Type: journal
- Metric_Type: total_item_investigations; total_item_requests; unique_item_investigations; unique_item_requests

For the purposes of TR_J4, the TR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Data_Type: journal
- Metric_Type: total_item_requests; unique_item_requests

TR FILTERS

TR can be filtered on six metrics, as described in the table below. It is also possible to exclude the month-by-month breakdown of activity and show only the total activity for the whole reporting period.

Filter / attribute	Description
YOP	All years, a specific year, or a range of years
Data_Type	All, or one or more of the Data_Types applicable to the title
Access_Type	All, or one or more of the Access_Types applicable to the title
Access_Method	All, or one or more of the Access_Methods applicable to the title
Metric_Type	All, or one or more of the Metric_Types applicable to the title
Section_Type	All, or one or more of the Section_Types applicable to the title
exclude_monthly_details	True or False. Show the Reporting_Period_Total column without month-by-month breakdowns

SCENARIO

Barbara wants to assess the usage from Journal X. She'd like to know what the total usage is, and how much of that usage is for OA_Gold articles. She therefore downloads the Title Master Report (TR). This shows:

- Access_Type: Controlled / Unique_Item_Requests: 49
- Access_Type: OA_Gold / Unique_Item_Requests: 18

Barbara then filters the TR using the YOP (Year of Publication) column, to eliminate the current year and show only articles in her perpetual access backfiles. The TR shows:

- Access_Type: Controlled / Unique_Item_Requests: 18
- Access_Type: OA_Gold / Unique_Item_Requests: 3

WHAT DOES A TR LOOK LIKE?

TRs are highly detailed and therefore quite lengthy. As well as the core information from the PR (Platform, Data_Type, Access_Method, Metric_Type, and Reporting_Period_Total), TR shows the title name and identifiers, the publisher details, Access_Type, Section_Type, and the year of publication (YOP), for a total of 17 columns plus monthly breakdowns.

Again, every metric type should be included, but for the purposes of this guide only a subset is shown in the example below.

Example: a TR has been generated for Journal Six on Publisher Platform Alpha (PP α) covering the period from 01 January to 30 June 2017, for Sample University. In this case, users from Sample University have investigated eight articles, and requested the fulltext for three of those articles.

<http://bit.ly/2mVpm3M>

Report_Name	Title Master Report
Report_ID	TR
Release	5
Institution_Name	Sample University
Institution_ID	isni=1234567890
Metric_Types	<i>as selected</i>

TITLE MASTER REPORT

Report_ Filters	<i>as selected</i>
Report_ Attributes	as selected
Exceptions	
Reporting_ Period	2017-01-01 to 2017-06-30
Created	2017-05-25
Created_By	Publisher Platform Alpha

Title	Pub-lisher	Pub-lisher_ ID	Plat- form	DOI	Proprietary_ ID	ISBN	Print_ ISSN	Online_ ISSN	URI	Data_ Type	Section_ Type	YOP	Access_ Type	Access_ Method	Metric_ Type	Re- porting_ Period_ Total
Journal Six	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	10.1000/xyz123	xyz123			1110987654321		Journal	Article	2016	Con- trolled	Regular	Total_ Item_ Investi- gations	8
Journal Six	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	10.1000/xyz123	xyz123			1110987654321		Journal	Article	2016	Con- trolled	Regular	Unique_ Item_ Investi- gations	8
Journal Six	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	10.1000/xyz123	xyz123			1110987654321		Journal	Article	2016	Con- trolled	Regular	Unique_ Title_ Investi- gations	1
Journal Six	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	10.1000/xyz123	xyz123			1110987654321		Journal	Article	2016	Con- trolled	Regular	Total_ Item_ Requests	3
Journal Six	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	10.1000/xyz123	xyz123			1110987654321		Journal	Article	2016	Con- trolled	Regular	Unique_ Item_ Requests	3
Journal Six	Gamma	1234_gam	PPα	10.1000/xyz123	xyz123			1110987654321		Journal	Article	2016	Con- trolled	Regular	Unique_ Title_ Requests	1

ITEM MASTER REPORT

Two Host Types need to provide an Item Master Report (IR):

1. Multimedia
2. Repository

An Item Master Report (IR) shows activity across all metrics for single items, such as articles or videos. IR can be filtered according to user needs, and has two Standard Views. IR has an additional filter, Section_Type, in addition to the five which apply to all of the Master Reports.

Identifier	Name	Description
IR_A1	Journal Article Requests	A pre-set Standard View of IR showing total item requests for journal articles
IR_M1	Multimedia Item Requests	A pre-set Standard View of IR showing total item requests for multimedia items

For the purposes of IR_A1, the IR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Data_Type: journal
- Section_Type: article
- Metric_Type: total_item_requests

Alternatively, IR_A1 may be specified using

- Access_Method: regular
- Data_Type: article
- Metric_Type: total_item_requests

For the purposes of IR_M1, the DR is pre-filtered using the following specification:

- Access_Method: regular
- Data_Type: multimedia
- Metric_Type: total_item_requests

IR FILTERS

IR can be filtered on various metrics, as described in the table below. It is also possible to include component details, and to exclude the month-by-month breakdown of activity.

Filter / attribute	Description
YOP	All years, a specific year, or a range of years
Data_Type	All, or one or more of the Data_Types applicable to the title
Access_Type	All, or one or more of the Access_Types applicable to the title
Access_Method	All, or one or more of the Access_Methods applicable to the title
Metric_Type	All, or one or more of the Metric_Types applicable to the title
include_component_details	True or False. Show the sub-units of the item
exclude_monthly_details	True or False. Show the Reporting_Period_Total column without month-by-month breakdowns

WHAT DOES AN IR LOOK LIKE?

An IR contains so much detail that it is not possible to show an example report here; visit <http://bit.ly/2n0w34m> to see an example. The column heads associated with an IR cover the item itself, its parent, and its component parts, and appear in the IR in this order:

- Item
- Parent_DOI
- Component_Title
- Publisher
- Parent_Proprietary_ID
- Component_Authors
- Publisher_ID
- Parent_ISBN
- Component_Data_Type
- Platform
- Parent_Print_ISSN
- Component_DOI
- Authors
- Parent_Online_ISSN
- Component_Proprietary_ID
- Publication_Date
- Parent_URI
- Component_ISBN
- Article_Version
- Component_Title
- Component_Print_ISSN
- DOI
- Component_Authors
- Component_Online_ISSN
- Proprietary_ID
- Component_Publication_Date
- Component_URI
- ISBN
- Component_Data_Type
- Data_Type
- Print_ISSN
- Component_DOI
- Section_Type
- Online_ISSN
- Component_Proprietary_ID
- YOP
- URI
- Component_ISBN
- Access_Type
- Parent_Title
- Component_Print_ISSN
- Access_Method
- Parent_Authors
- Parent_Print_ISSN
- Metric_Type
- Parent_Publication_Date
- Parent_Online_ISSN
- Reporting_Period_Total
- Parent_Article_Version
- Parent_URI
- Mmm-yyyy
- Parent_Data_Type

ATTRIBUTES, ELEMENTS, AND OTHER (SLIGHTLY) TECHY THINGS

Release 5 of the COUNTER Code of Practice has added a series of elements and attributes to our long-standing metrics. These help to provide much more granular information in an organized way, as well as letting the COUNTER team maintain and amend the Code of Practice over time.

HOST TYPE

Your Host Type determines which of the Master Reports you need to produce. A single platform might fit multiple Host Types; if you aren't sure what your Host Type is, please send a question to the COUNTER team through our website.

Host Type	Description
A&I Database	Databases containing Abstract and Index information but no fulltext
Aggregated Full Content	Aggregated pre-set databases of fulltext and other content where content is accessed in the context of the licensed database
Data Repository	Access to data rather than fulltext content; includes subject repositories, institution, department, etc.
Discovery Service	A central index of article, book and other metadata
eBook Collection	Book content provided as fixed collections that behave like databases
eBook	Book content provided as individual titles or packages
eJournal	Serial content as individual titles or packages.
Full Content Database	Non-aggregated databases of fulltext content
Multimedia Collection	Audio, video or other multimedia content as fixed collections that behave like databases
Multimedia	Audio, video or other multimedia content as individual items
Repository	Provides access to an institution's research output; includes subject repositories, institution, department, etc.
Scholarly Collaboration Network	A service used by researchers to share information about their work

ATTRIBUTE: DATA_TYPE

Data_Type is used to group content at the level of the Title. Depending on your Host Type, you will need to apply different Data_Types.

- **Article:** an individual content object, usually published as part of a journal or reference work
- **Book Segment:** a book segment (e.g. chapter, section label, etc.).
- **Book:** a monograph text
- **Database:** a fixed database where content is searched and accessed in the context of the database
- **Dataset:** a data set.
- **Journal:** textual content published serially as a journal or magazine
- **Multimedia:** multimedia content, such as audio, images, or video.
- **Newspaper or Newsletter:** textual content published serially in a newspaper or newsletter.
- **Platform:** the “Title” of the item being reported on is a content platform and may reflect usage from multiple data types.
- **Report:** a report.
- **Repository Item:** generic classification used for items stored in a repository
- **Thesis or Dissertation:** a dissertation of thesis
- **Other:** the content item cannot be classified by any of the other data types.

SCENARIO

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on Publisher Platform Alpha. From a list of search results, she opens three article abstracts and a video record. The relevant Data_Types are:

- Journal
- Multimedia

ATTRIBUTE: SECTION_TYPE

Some Data_Types are delivered in small sub-units, which is where Section_Type comes in.

- **Article:** a sub-unit of Data_Types Journal and Book
- **Book:** a sub-unit of Data_Types Platform and Database
- **Chapter:** a sub-unit of Data_Types Book and Book Segment
- **Section:** a sub-unit of Data_Types Book and Book Segment
- **Other:** content delivered in sections that are not otherwise represented on the list

SCENARIO

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on Publisher Platform Alpha. From a list of search results, she opens three article abstracts and a video record. The relevant Section_Type is:

- Article

ATTRIBUTE: ACCESS_TYPE

Access_Type allows us to determine whether content was Open Access or not. For the Host Types eBook, eJournal, Multimedia and Repository, only two Access_Types are needed:

- **OA_Gold:** content available under a Gold Open Access license from the point of publication
- **Controlled:** everything which is not OA_Gold

The Repository Host Type also needs to provide a third Access_Type:

- **Other_Free_To_Read:** content which is not OA_Gold, but which is freely available to read without a license

SCENARIO

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on Publisher Platform Alpha. From a list of search results, she opens three article abstracts and a video record. None of the articles is Open Access, but one is freely available as part of a marketing drive. The relevant Access_Type is:

- Controlled

Susan then selects a new article from the search results list, from a Gold Open Access journal. The relevant Access_Type is:

- OA_Gold

ATTRIBUTE: ACCESS_METHOD

Access_Method applies when a Host allows Text and Data Mining (TDM) of their content, and is able to distinguish TDM activity from all other activity, for example because they have a specific TDM API. The valid Access_Method attributes are

- **Regular:** all activity which is not TDM
- **TDM:** text and data mining activity

ATTRIBUTE: YOP

YOP stands for Year of Publication: the four-digit year in which the Version of Record was published. Where the YOP is undefined:

- Use “9999” for in press articles
- Use “0001” for content with an unknown YOP

SCENARIO

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on Publisher Platform Alpha. From a list of search results, she opens three article abstracts and a video record. One article was from 2017, one was in press, and one had an unknown date of publication. The relevant YOPs are:

- 2017
- 9999
- 0001

PUTTING IT ALL TOGETHER

This section walks through a scenario and uses the information to put together a set of COUNTER Release 5 reports.

ABOUT THE PLATFORM

Publisher Platform Alpha (PP α) hosts a combination of materials: 100 fulltext journals, 750 fulltext books, and a multimedia database. This means that PP α falls under several Host Types: Aggregated Full Content, eBooks, eJournals, and Multimedia Collection.

Given the Host Types, we know that PP α needs to provide all four of the Master Reports and all of the Standard Views.

ABOUT THE SUBSCRIBING INSTITUTION

Institution Omega subscribes to the entire journals list on PP α , as well as the multimedia database. They do not subscribe to the books list.

SCENARIO: SUSAN'S ACTIVITY

Susan is researching the history of antibiotics on PP α . She runs a search across the entire platform (that is, she does not limit her search to the multimedia database).

From the list of search results, Susan opens the following items:

- 2 article abstracts from Journal of Antibiotics are Fun
- 1 article abstract from Journal of Medical Historical Trivia
- 1 video from the multimedia database
- 1 chapter abstract from The Big Book of Medical Marvels
- 1 book abstract of A Medical History Reference

This activity triggers a whole series of investigation metrics, as well as some access denials. Note that because Susan's institution has no license to access book content, Release 5 counts two access denials even though she has only attempted to access the abstracts at this point.

After reading the abstracts, Susan triggers additional investigation and access denial metrics, as well as some request metrics, by:

- Downloading 2 article full-text PDFs from Journal of Antibiotics are Fun
- Watching 1 video from the multimedia database
- Attempting to download 1 chapter PDF from The Big Book of Medical Marvels

Note that Susan's attempt to download a chapter from The Big Book of Medical Marvels counts as an investigation but does not count as a request. This is because her institution has not licensed books, and therefore her access is denied.

IN SUMMARY

Collecting all of this together, Susan's session on PPα results in a whole series of metrics which will be available to her librarian through any of the four Master Reports, or six Standard Views, for delivery to Institution Omega.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

An active participant in the scholarly publishing community, Tasha is a member of the COUNTER Executive and organises the annual Digital Publishing conference for STM. Her industry expertise stretches from publishing operations and project management to policy setting, via technology management and business analysis. Tasha can be found on LinkedIn at <https://www.linkedin.com/in/tashamc/>

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